

Letter to the Editor

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The “Embrace Project”: facilitating the health care professionals in diagnosis, clinical reasoning and virtuous co-management of chronic patients before, during and after the COVID-19 pandemic in Italy

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To the Editor,

According to the World Health Organization, 70–80% of world healthcare resources are allocated to the management of chronic diseases [1]. About 55% of contacts with General Practitioners (GPs) in Italy are generated by chronic patients [2] and 48.7% of subjects aged 65–74 are affected by at least two chronic diseases [1]. The Italian National Health Service was born in 1978, establishing a universal and unlimited system of care. In 1992 the healthcare system was reformed: the State determines the essential levels of assistance whilst the Regions have exclusive competence in the regulation, organization and financing of local health services. The National Chronicity Plan (NCP) was born in 2016 from the need to harmonize activities and provide a common strategic direction in this field [1]. Compatibly with the availability of economic, human and structural resources, the chronic patient

should be ideally followed mainly at home, creating individualized care paths integrating hospital and primary care. The coexistence of multiple diseases may require the intervention of several professional figures, with high risk of fragmented interventions, lack of integration of the care services and absence of a single point of reference and coordination. As a consequence, the patient involvement in the care process and adherence to interventions might be difficult, triggering severe delays in diagnosis, sub-optimal disease management with progression and onset of additional comorbidities and disabilities, having a great impact not only on the individual but on the whole society, due to the associated incremental costs. Hence, within the current organization of the Italian National Health Service (NHS), the GP may take a key role with full ownership of the patient journey. In the past, the GP was considered first as a “gatekeeper”, mainly responsible for controlling healthcare expenditure and compliance with drug use, and then as a “case manager”, as patient services coordinator with more managerial than clinical skills. There is a great need to evolve the GP to become a generalist for “low risk” diseases and a specialist for some chronic diseases, with proper medical education and equipped with modern tools, including digital innovation. This has become dramatically evident in the days of the COVID-19 emergent pandemic, when the primary care was essential not only in managing patients infected with SARS-Cov2 but also chronic patients not infected but unable to get assistance from hospitals entirely switched to manage severe COVID-19 patients [3]. In light of this scenario, there is therefore even a greater need to optimize the chronic patient’s care path to improve health outcomes and use the available resources efficiently. Below we want to describe the “Embrace Project” that, operating in full

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tele-consultations, remote assistance to quarantined individuals, digital repetition of medical prescriptions, was essential to manage emergent COVID-19 patients as well as to continue managing chronic patients. Similarly, vast majority of interactions between EAs and GPs switched from traditional face-to face contacts to remote modes (i.e., video-calls, webinars). Although initially perceived as surrogate, it became soon evident how such digital interactions might represent valid alternative options and becoming part of the standard practice in the post-COVID-19 era. Although the identification of patients was quicker than expected, in most of the cases the recall was based on manual screening of clinical records. A digital approach applying artificial intelligence to GPs clinical databases would represent a formidable accelerator. Hence, the Embrace Project is evolving as well by implementing digital initiatives based on the IBM Watson platform to connect all stakeholders and move together towards a proactive partnership with the patient, transforming the unpleasant journey in a new opportunity for enjoying life. Such initiatives may allow measuring the impact of the Embrace project on the efficiency of the health system with more sophisticated qualitative endpoints, in the light of a value based approach that should become the standard approach in the hard times we are going to face in the post-COVID-19 era. Results will be shared in future communications.

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